

Interactions of L-amino acids with metronidazole and tinidazole

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The possibility of interaction of amino acids with known drugs metronidazole (MDZ) and tinidazole (TDZ) has been explored. The amino acids (AA) have been found to form fairly stable complexes with MDZ and TDZ as apparent from the association constants of AA + MDZ and AA + TDZ complexes in water determined spectrophotometrically using an iterative procedure. The AA + MDZ complexes have been found to be more stable compared to AA + TDZ complexes.

Most of the compounds of medicinal interest undergo a number of complicated interactions of varied nature. But the action of a drug in a biological system is the ultimate consequences of physicochemical interactions^{1,2} between the drug and functionally important molecules in the living organisms known as receptor², a portion of the bacteria or microbe etc. of the respective aetiological agent. However, the drugs may be structurally specific when they have structural and biochemical specificity to interact with the receptors or structurally non-specific where a number of physicochemical properties produce the drug action³.

A large number of compounds with varying structures and properties have been used as amoebicides⁴. However, two important antifungal and antiprotozoal agents metronidazole and tinidazole have been widely used in the treatment of intestinal and extraintestinal amoebiasis.

The action of the drug is probably an example of drug-receptor interaction as the drugs are well absorbed by proteins and studies with calf-thymus DNA indicate that the reduced metronidazole causes a loss of the helical structure of DNA, strand breakage and loss of its function as a template⁴. However, the receptors generally have a large number of binding sites where the drugs may be bound but accurate and complete topography of the receptors are not known³. Naturally, the exact nature of interactions and the exact sites of binding are not known.

Strong irreversible covalent bonding of drugs with receptors are usually obtainable in a few cases, but in most cases, drugs interact reversibly and form weak bonds with receptors. Different types of weak forces like hydrogen bonding, charge-transfer interactions, hydrophobic interactions etc. are involved.

These considerations led us to study spectrophotometrically the interactions of different amino acids and some other

compounds like uracil, caffeine with two known amoebicides metronidazole and tinidazole. The results are presented in this communication.

Results and Discussion

The equilibrium constants of the complexes have been determined assuming the composition of the complexes to be 1 : 1 but they have not been verified by Job's method of continuous variations or by other methods. The correctness of the assumption has been verified from the consistency of the results obtained from the derived equation based on 1 : 1 complex formation.

The association constant (K) for the complex between amino acid (A) (also uracil, caffeine) and drugs (D),

can be written as

$$K = \frac{[AD]}{[A][D]} \times \frac{\gamma_{AD}}{\gamma_A \times \gamma_D} \approx \frac{[AD]}{[A][D]} \quad (2)$$

Since the solutions contain neutral molecules and the concentrations of A and D are extremely low (5 to 2×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³), it is reasonable to assume $\gamma_{AD}/\gamma_A\gamma_D$ to be unity.

The equation utilised for the calculation of K ⁵ is (when A, D and AD absorb in the same region),

$$\frac{C_1}{d - d_1 - d_2} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)l} + \frac{1}{K(C_2 - X)(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)l} \quad (3)$$

($l = 1$ cm), where C_1 , C_2 are the concentrations of A and D respectively, and X is the concentration of the complex determined from the relation,

$$X = \frac{(d - d_1 - d_2)}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)l} \quad (4)$$

where d_1 , d_2 , d and ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , ϵ are the absorbances and molar absorptivities of A, D and AD respectively.

Since, the amino acids under considerations do not absorb, the modified equation,

$$\frac{C_1}{d - d_2} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)(C_2 - X)Kl} \quad (5)$$

is used, where

$$X = \frac{d - d_2}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)l} \quad (6)$$

d_2 , d and ϵ_2 , ϵ are the absorbances and molar absorptivities of the drug and the complex respectively. X has been assumed to be small initially and neglected. Approximate values of $1/(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ or $1/(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)$ and X (from equation 6) have been obtained from the plot of $C_1/(d - d_1 - d_2)$ [or $C_1/(d - d_2)$] against $1/C_2$. The value of X has been utilised to calculate refined values of K , $1/(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ [or $1/(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)$] and X . The iteration has been repeated till constancy in K and $(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)$ have been obtained. Generally, one to two iterations are sufficient to determine K and ϵ values. The K and ϵ values of the complexes (Table 1) have been found sufficiently high.

Both metronidazole (MDZ) and tinidazole (TDZ) are fairly soluble in water. They absorb strongly in the uv-region. The maxima near 230 nm appear to be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi$ transition whereas those near 320 nm appear to be due to $n \rightarrow \pi$ transition.

The amino acid-drug interaction is characterised by the changes in the absorbances and slight or almost no change in the absorption maxima (Table 2). However, the values of the association constants of the drugs with amino acids show that the drugs interact fairly strongly with uracil, caffeine as well as with amino acids. The association constants are arranged in order of increasing stability (Table 1) of the complexes. Naturally, all the drugs have the capability to interact with amino acids. The greater the stability of the complex, the greater is the probability of attachment. It has been found that metronidazole complexes are slightly more stable than the tinidazole complexes. The replacement of OH by SO_2Et group is apparently the reason but the site of action is probably not $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ group or $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_2\text{Et}$ group but elsewhere.

It is apparent that the sequence of stability of the complexes cannot be correlated with the acidity or basicity of the amino acids. However, since the solutions have pH between 6 and 7, most of the amino acids are present predominantly as negatively charged ions.

Table 1. Charge transfer complexes of metronidazole and tinidazole with amino acids and uracil, caffeine and K and ϵ values

Amino acids	Tinidazole			Metronidazole		
	$10^{-3} K$	$10^{-3} \epsilon$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$10^{-3} K$	$10^{-3} \epsilon$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹
Uracil	0.63	2.33	15.97	0.69	9.00	16.20
Caffeine	0.85	2.75	16.71	0.91	9.55	16.88
L-Aspartic acid	1.12	3.28	17.39	1.25	11.00	17.66
L-Methionine	2.01	5.36	18.84	2.18	15.00	19.05
L-Lysine	2.39	7.78	19.27	2.52	21.80	19.40
L-Proline	2.70	10.12	19.57	2.88	22.30	19.73
L-Cystine	3.00	21.60	19.84	3.22	23.10	20.01
L-Valine	3.59	22.00	20.28	3.76	26.20	20.39
L-Glutamine	4.14	22.50	20.63	4.31	27.00	20.74
L-Leucine	4.70	23.20	20.95	4.85	28.10	21.02
L-Asparagine	5.01	24.50	21.10	5.15	29.90	21.17
L-Glutamic acid	5.29	25.50	21.24	5.41	31.20	21.30

Table 2. Absorption maxima (nm) of drugs, complexes and uracil, caffeine in water

Amino acids	λ_{max} (amino acid)	Tinidazole (λ_{max} 316.5) (λ_{max} (complex))	Metronidazole (λ_{max} 318.9) (λ_{max} (complex))
Uracil	258	316.9, 256.8	319.7, 257.2
Caffeine	278.2	316.9, 280.2	318.9, 280.2
L-Aspartic acid	-	317.3	319.3
L-Methionine	-	316.9	319.7
L-Lysine	-	316.4	318.2
L-Proline	-	316.9	319.3
L-Cystine	-	317.3	319.3
L-Valine	-	317.3	319.3
L-Glutamine	-	317.3	319.3
L-Leucine	-	317.3	319.3
L-Asparagine	-	317.3	319.3
L-Glutamic acid	-	316.9	318.1

It is known that the amino acids like leucine, valine containing hydrocarbon moieties have inbuilt capability to permit intramolecular hydrophobic bonding⁶ between the amino acids and intermolecular interactions with hydrophobic areas of drug molecules and those of amino acids. Thus, hydrophobic interactions between the hydrophobic groups of A and D or charge transfer interactions may be the reasons of drug-amino acid interactions. But nothing specific can

